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INTERDISCIPLINARY ENGINEERING EDUCATION, LINKING DIFFERENT DISCIPLINES BOTH INSIDE AND OUTSIDE ENGINEERING LINKING WITH SOCIETY

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How to use an assessment as learning (AAL) approach within authentic interdisciplinary learning environments

Solutions to complex societal, political and economic challenges increasingly are developed during interdisciplinary collaboration. This in turn entails curricula to prepare students for working in interdisciplinary projects. It requires students to broaden their perspective across disciplines and relate their own subject knowledge to knowledge of other subject areas and develop their problem solving skills. In our experience, one of the challenges with interdisciplinary project work is how to assess the work of students. The foci, scope and range of authentic assignments make it hard to construct generic criteria against which students can be assessed. Additionally, using generic criteria implies a risk that assessment takes place on a shallow level and does not engage students to take responsibility for their own learning. The challenge is to change the mere focus on summative assessment towards forms of formative assessment, in order to help students gain insight in their learning process and to support them in this process.

A possible solution for these challenges is implementing *assessment as learning*, where the focus is on student learning and development, and where assessment is used as a learning instrument. It emphasizes learner agency which entails that students have control over what and how they learn within the boundaries of the authentic learning environment. Continuous formative constructive feedback is a key element to help improve and maintain focus on learning.

When a summative verdict is necessary, through using an assessment as learning approach, at the end, the result of this summative judgment should not be a surprise for students anymore, since they already have received frequent formative feedback, feedup and feedforward and adjusted their learning accordingly.

Currently, we are developing an assessment as learning approach in the Smart Solution Semester of Saxion University of Applied Sciences, where third-year students from three or more (engineering) disciplines work together in project teams on large (25 ECTS) projects, provided by research groups and the business community. In this semester, students are assessed on their learning outcomes by using a portfolio assessment. The assessment revolves around three domains: usage of knowledge of own and other disciplines, professional skills, and developing research competences and an inquiry mindset. Additionally, a pilot is currently in progress in which students set their own learning goals and monitor these goals during the course of the Semester. Students frequently seek and receive formative feedback during the semester through feedback from peers, tutors, and experts.

Workshop design

In this workshop, we will provide recent insights from research on assessment as learning, and provide several illustrative examples from our experiences in the semester. Additionally, participants will work on a case -either from their own practice to translate a more traditional assessment method to an assessment as learning approach.

Overarching learning goal: Participants understand the key features and strengths and weaknesses of an assessment as learning approach and relate these to the methods of assessment that are used in their own practice.

Introduction (15 min.)

Assessment as learning within the Smart Solutions Semester – our experience
We will explain briefly the key elements of ‘assessment as learning’ from literature and share our experience with the implementation of this approach within the context of the Smart Solutions Semester. For every key element we will provide examples from practice. The focus will be on different types of formative evaluation and the value of continues constructive feedback.

Assignment in small ‘break out’groups (15 min.)

- Based on the previously shared key elements of an AAL approach participants analyze an example from their own practice where students work together in (multidisciplinary) groups. A framework for analysis is provided.
- On a Padlet they write down the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats they see when using an AAL approach in their own practice.
- In small groups they will discuss the analysis. What similarities are there and what differences? Together with the moderator they will draw an overarching conclusion to whether this approach would be feasible for their context..

Evaluation assignment whole group (5 min.)

We will invite participants to share the overall conclusions of their subgroup. Conclusions will be discussed in relation to the key elements of AAL.

Evaluation (5 min.)

Short evaluation of the workshop

The main question in the evaluation will be: ‘What will you do different now after this workshop?’ In other words, what are new insights you have gained or what will you test/implement in your own practice?